

Effect of Selected Play Therapy on Hospitalization related Anxiety among School Age Children admitted in selected Paediatric Ward

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Abstract— Hospitalization represents a hostile and unfamiliar event for the child, as hospital procedures and therapeutic treatments that can cause pain as well as physical and psychological suffering. The school-age child is able to present some understanding about the disease, but still vulnerable to events that diminish their sense of control and power. Thus, the child needs to receive appropriate and atraumatic assistance for their recovery in order to minimize the stress generated by hospitalization. In this sense, the company of their family and implementation of recreational activities in hospital settings are recommended and studies have demonstrated this can reduce stress and anxiety. The professional training of nurses provides resources that enable the negative emotional state of hospitalized children to be alleviated, one of which is sand tray therapy

Problem statement: Effect of selected play Therapy on Hospitalization related Anxiety among School Age Children admitted in selected Pediatric Ward.

Objectives

1. To find the level of hospitalization related anxiety.
2. To find the effect of sand tray therapy on hospitalization related anxiety.

Methodology

Quantitative research approach is used 70 hospitalized school age children were selected. Simple random technique used for the data collection. Data was collected by using research tool which had two section. Section A including Socio demographical variables and Section B Parent observed behavior check list on children's anxiety .

Analysis of data was done by using fisher's exact test and Mann-Whitney test

Result : In Pre test, 31.4% had moderate anxiety, 50% had severe anxiety, 18.6% had profound anxiety and after the intervention in post test 58% had mild level of anxiety, 12% had moderate anxiety and none of them had severe and profound anxiety. The effect of sand tray therapy was seen on hospitalization related anxiety among school age children admitted in selected paediatric ward. Mean value of anxiety score in pretest was 121.26 and in the post test was 65.76 . Wilcoxon's statistical test administered with the score of 7.28 which is significant at p value <0.0001, that shows that sand therapy is effective in reducing hospitalization related anxiety

Conclusion

The results of this study revealed that the children who received sand tray therapy during hospitalization had a statistically significant reduction in anxiety. Sand tray therapy is demonstrated to be effective in reducing the anxiety of hospitalized school age children. Sand tray therapy is highly recommended because it is effective , easy to carry out and inexpensive.

Keywords— selected play therapy,Sand Tray, hospitalization, Anxiety , hospitalized children,

I. INTRODUCTION

Every year many children are admitted to hospitals. This can have several reasons, both acute and planned hospital stays, may be threatening and stressful for many children. The subsequent emotions - anxiety, fear, worry, stress, panic, and uncertainty- can hinder an optimized healing process. Moreover, psychological health problems can result from high levels of anxiety in children, likewise negative effects on their behavioral, cognitive, emotional and academic development. These unfavorable outcomes stress the importance of reducing the anxiety level of hospitalized children.1

The concepts of health and illness are changing. The segment of lifespan that extends from age 6 years to 12 years has a variety of labels. As children enter the school years, their play takes on new dimensions that reflect a new stage of development. Hospitalization and prolonged illness can retard growth and development and cause adverse reactions in the child based on stages of development. During hospitalization and prolonged illness, the children are concerned with fear, worry, fantasies, modesty, and privacy. Nurses should play a vital role in helping the children and the family members to cope effectively with hospitalization. Children are free from anxiety and other hospital-related stresses. Also they learn colors, numbers sizes, and shapes through play by using sand tray therapy by depicting the story, and the child enhances their creative skills and gets diverted from their illness and parental separation.

Play therapy have major role in preventing the anxiety among school age children. Play therapy refers to wide variety of treatment methods all of which incorporate the use of play. For children, play is a natural method of learning, development and expression of feeling, thoughts and concerns. Play therapy offers a natural, safe and non-invasive method to foster and hasten recovery from anxiety such as social anxiety, separation anxiety etc. It has been specifically designed to be developmentally appropriate for children and is based on the idea that children communicate and express inner feelings and conflict through play. The value of play to a sick child in the hospital has long been recognized and if the hospital is to meet the physical, mental and emotional need of the child. It must also provide suitable play activity to the child to reduce the fear and anxiety of hospitalized children.

Play activities can be used in a multitude of setting and in multidisciplinary fashion Ziegler state that one of every four children will be hospitalized at least once before reaching school age. The physical and psychosocial stress of hospitalization may be influences by the child developmental level, causing behavior changes, somatic complaints and a prolonged hospital stay. Other purposes of therapeutic play are helps sick children gradually regain independence through enjoiment of group experiences. Creativity can be developed through playing with toys, games and group projects during the literature review, the investigator came across studies in relation to play activity and its effectiveness, in reducing the child anxiety, which are done in foreign settings. Studies done regarding the relationship between play activities and anxiety of hospitalized children are very few in India. Thus the investigators were motivated to carry out this study.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Effect of Sand Tray Therapy on Hospitalization related Anxiety among School Age Children admitted in selected Pediatric Ward.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find the level of hospitalization related anxiety.
2. To find the effect of sand tray therapy on hospitalization related anxiety.

IV. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

Sand tray therapy: In this study, it refers to a therapeutic technique that uses a tray of sand along with small tools, toys, or figurines to help people express themselves without words.

V. HYPOTHESIS

H₀-There is no association between sand tray therapy on hospitalization related anxiety at the level of 0.05

V. ASSUMPTION

1. Hospitalized children are susceptible to develop anxiety.
2. Children are explicit the reactions of hospitalization: separation anxiety, social anxiety,
3. depression.

VI. ETHICAL ASPECTS

1. The proposal of the study was presented to Institutional Ethical Committee. The study commenced after the approval of the committee.
2. Informed consent will be taken from the participants
3. Confidentiality of the records will be maintained by the researcher.
4. Subjects must be protected from all types of harm.

VII. RESEARCH DESIGN

The researcher has adopted Quasi experimental One group (pre test post test only research design) to assess the effect of sand tray therapy on hospitalization related anxiety among school age children admitted in selected pediatric ward.

This is at par with aim of research where researcher wants to assess the level of hospitalization related anxiety among school age children. In addition to this, to assess the effect of Sand Tray Therapy on hospitalization related anxiety.

The study has been conducted in the inpatient department of super speciality hospitals. The hospitals were situated in the urban area. The reason for selecting these hospitals is administrative support and co-operation, availability of samples, convenience for transportation.

A. Inclusion criteria

- Children in the age group of 6 to 10 years.
- Children who are admitted in medical ward irrespective of any illness.
- Children who can understand and able to speak English, Hindi, Marathi.

B. Exclusion Criteria

- Children who are blind, mentally and physically challenged.
- Children admitted only for observation.
- Children having skin allergy.
- Children who are critically ill and unconscious.
- Children who post-operative, bedridden and surgeries related to hands.

C. Description of The Tool

Section A: Deals with demographic data. consists of demographic variables of age, gender of the child, birth order, religion, family type, residence, income, educational status of the father and mother, education of the child, dietary pattern.

Section B: Parent observed behavior check list on children's anxiety. It consists of 36 items, and the scores are in Likert scale of 1, 2, 3, 4 & 5, for each behavior.

Scoring Procedure: The scoring system is divided into following categories

- 0 to 36 ---- No Anxiety
- 37 o 72 ---- Mild anxiety
- 73 to 108 ---- Moderate anxiety
- 109 to 144 ---- Severe anxiety
- 145 to 180 ---- Profound Anxiety

D. Method Of Data Collection:

Permission From Concern Authorities Prior to the collection of data permission was obtain from the Directors' academics of the selected hospital and HOD's of the respected area. The purpose and nature of the study were explained to authority to gain cooperation.

Period Of Data Collection :

Data collection process began from May-June 2024 each subject was explained about the study and its purpose. The data collection was done strictly under standard conditions. The criteria of sampling were kept in mind while selecting the samples. Samples were selected as per the criterion mention in the study.

Pocess Of Data Collection :

- School age children admitted in pediatric ward were approached for participating in the research study.
- Participants were enrolled as per inclusion and exclusion criteria approved earlier.
- Children’s who were willing to participate in the study their assent and parent’s written informed consent was obtained.
- The parents were interviewed to collect the pretest data regarding socio demographic and child behavior during hospitalization.
- This was followed by interview to gain information related to hospitalization related anxiety among school age children admitted in selected pediatric ward.
- Children’s were given sand tray with small miniatures for 30 min for 1 week.
- Children’s were told to depict the story or explore the world into the sand tray which is present in their mind.
- After 30 min the discussion was carried on the sand tray.
- Post test was conducted after the discussion to known the level of hospitalized anxiety present in the school age children’s.

E. *Plan Of Data Analysis*

The data analysis was planned to include descriptive and inferential statistics and present them in form of tables, graphs and figures. The data was set in excel file, and analysis done by wilcoxon test, fisher test and mann-whitney test using statistical test.

VIII. RESULT

Section I: - Description Of Samples By Frequency And Percentage Of Hospitalization Related Anxiety Among School Age Children.

TABLE I
ASSESS THE LEVEL OF HOSPITALIZATION RELATED ANXIETY AMONG SCHOOL AGE CHILDREN
n=70

Level of anxiety	Pre test (%)	Post test (%)
36 – 72 (Mild)	0	58 (82.9)
73 – 108 (Moderate)	22 (31.4)	12 (17.1)
109 – 144 (Severe)	35 (50)	0
145 – 180 (Profound)	13 (18.6)	0
Total	70 (100)	70 (100)

- Table I shows majority of samples 35 (50) reported to have severe level of anxiety,22 (31.4) belongs to moderate level of anxiety,13 (18.6) reported to have profound level of anxiety and whereas none of the sample reported to have mild level of anxiety in the pre test.
- In the post test majority of samples 58 (82.9) reported to have mild level of anxiety,12 (17.1) belongs to moderate level of anxiety, whereas none of the samples reported to have severe and profound level of anxiety

Section II: - Analysis Of Area Wise Effect Of Sand Tray Therapy On Hospitalization Related Anxiety

TABLE II
AREA WISE EFFECT OF SAND TRAY THERAPY ON HOSPITALIZATION RELATED ANXIETY

Area of anxiety related to	Pre test		Post test		Wilcoxon Z Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD			
Separation	28.79	4.436	17.97	5.330	7.30	<0.0001	37.58
Gaze behaviors	5.86	2.757	3.07	1.448	6.85	<0.0001	47.61
Vocalization	26.23	5.509	13.59	2.476	7.30	<0.0001	48.19
Loss of control	12.31	3.851	5.70	1.797	6.60	<0.0001	53.70
Bodily injury	24.51	7.952	12.19	2.481	7.29	<0.0001	50.27
Co-operation	23.56	5.442	13.24	2.651	7.29	<0.0001	43.80

n=70

GRAPH I
AREA WISE EFFECT OF SAND TRAY THERAPY ON HOSPITALIZATION RELATED ANXIETY

Table II and graph I shows that the mean value of separation anxiety in pretest was 28.79 and in the post test the mean value was 17.97 (37.58%) which indicates decreased level of separation anxiety as p value is <0.0001. The mean value of gaze behaviors in pretest was 5.86 and in post test the mean value was 3.07 (47.61%) which indicates decreased level of gaze behaviors as p value is <0.0001. The mean value of vocalization in pretest was 26.23 and in post test the mean value was 13.59 (48.19%) which indicates decreased level of vocalization as p value is <0.0001. The mean value of loss of control in pretest was 12.31 and in post test the mean value was 5.70 (53.70%) which indicates decreased level of loss of control as p value is <0.0001. The mean value of bodily injury in pretest was 24.51 and in post test the mean value was 12.19 (50.27%) which indicates decreased level of bodily injury as p value is <0.0001. The mean value of co-operation in pretest was 23.56 and in post test the mean value was 13.24 (43.80%) which indicates decreased level of co-operation as p value is <0.0001.

Section III: - Analysis Of Effect Of Sand Tray Therapy On Hospitalization Related Anxiety.

TABLE III
EFFECT OF SAND TRAY THERAPY ON HOSPITALIZATION RELATED ANXIETY

Parameter	Pre test		Post test		Wilcoxon Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Anxiety score	121.26	24.121	65.76	13.377	7.28	<0.0001

n=70

Percentage change = 45.77%

GRAPH II
EFFECT OF SAND TRAY THERAPY ON HOSPITALIZATION RELATED ANXIETY

Table III and figure II shows the mean value of anxiety score in pre-test was 121.26 and in the post test was 65.76. Wilcoxon's statistical test administered with the score of 7.28 which is significant at P value <0.0001 , that shows the sand therapy is effective in reducing hospitalization related anxiety.

IX. DISCUSSION

A) *The Study Findings Was Consistent With The Study Done By Kinjal Patel (2014)*

In pre test majority of samples 11 (36.7) reported to have moderate level of anxiety, 10 (33.3) belongs to severe level of anxiety, 9 (30.0) reported to have mild level of anxiety. In post test majority of samples 17 (56.7) reported to have mild level of anxiety, 12 (40.0) belongs to severe level of anxiety, whereas only 1 (3.3) of the samples reported to have moderate level of anxiety.

B) *The study findings was consistent with the study done by titi xavier and sagayamary(2014)*

In experimental group pre test score was minimum 50 and maximum 58, and mean and SD was 53.4, 1.73 respectively. In experimental post test score was minimum was 242 and maximum was 248 and mean, and SD was 246.23, 1.38 respectively. The obtained t- value 491.04 statistically was significant at 0.05 level. So null hypothesis rejected and research hypothesis was accepted. So there was significant reduction in the level of anxiety among the children in experimental group. In the control group Pre-test score minimum was 51 and maximum was 56 and mean, and SD was 53.1, 1.8 respectively. In control group post test score minimum was 51 and maximum was 55 and mean, and SD was 52.97, 0.96 respectively. The obtained t- value is 0.724 statistically was not significant at 0.05 level, therefore null hypothesis was accepted and research hypothesis was rejected. It is inferred that the children in the pre –test and post test were not different with regarded to anxiety. It shows that they were a comparable group.

C) *The study findings was consistent with the study done by Aakanksha Bajpai, B S Ilayaraja, NV Muninarayanappa, Nageshwar V (2017)*

82% of the hospitalized children had severe anxiety, 8% had moderate anxiety while only 5% had mild anxiety. The study findings was consistent with the study done by Christy Susan Mathew, Daly Christabel (2018) In the experimental group, pre-test showed that 8 (40%) children had a moderate level of anxiety and 12 (60%) had a mild level of anxiety and in posttest, 2 (10%) had moderate level of anxiety and 18 (90%) experienced mild level of anxiety. None of the children had a severe level of anxiety. In the control group, pre-test shows 5 (25%) children had a moderate level of anxiety and 15 (75%) had a mild level of anxiety and in posttest, 3 (15%) had a moderate level of anxiety and 17 (85%) experienced mild level of anxiety.

D) *The study findings was consistent with the study done by Mrs. Sharmila Mahesh Kulal and Dr. Mrs. Supriya Pottal Ray (2020)*

This study shows that p value of per test of experimental and control group was 0.27 which is more than 0.05 (p value > 0.05) so there is no significant difference between experimental and control group pre test. Whereas in post test p value was less than 0.05 (p value < 0.05) so we reject H₀ (There was no significant difference between the pre and post level of anxiety among hospitalized children in experimental and control group at 0.05 level of significance).

E) *The study findings was consistent with the study done by Mr. Sunil Kumar Jaiswal, Mrs. Lubna, Mr. Akhil Kumar Pandey (2023)*

In the control group during pretest, 30% had mild level of anxiety, 26.7% had moderate level of anxiety and 43.3% had severe level of anxiety. In the post test, 30% had mild level of anxiety, 26.7% had moderate level of anxiety and 43.3% had severe level of anxiety. In experimental group before intervention 13.3% had mild level of anxiety, 40% had moderate level of anxiety and the remaining 46.7% had severe level of anxiety. In the post test, 13.3% had no anxiety, 43.3% had mild level of anxiety and the remaining 43.3% had moderate level of anxiety. The effectiveness of clay therapy on anxiety among by using un-paired "t"-test. The obtained t-value between experimental and control group anxiety is 4.61 at p-value 0.0001 level of significance

X. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- This study was done on a small sample size of 70; hence generalization is possible only for the selected subjects from selected hospital.
- The researcher found little difficulty in getting cooperation from the children.

XI. RECOMMENDATION

1. A similar study can be conducted in a larger sample.
2. Similar study can be conducted among different age groups and for mentally challenged patients in different settings.
3. A comparison study with drawing and clay, or clay and storytelling, clay and music, clay and dance can be done to determine the effect of sand therapy in the level of anxiety.
4. A longitudinal study can be conducted to assess the effect of sand therapy on anxiety of the children.
5. The study can be done to compare the effects of sand therapy for anxiety and cancer pain children.

XII. CONCLUSION

The results of this study revealed that the children who received sand tray therapy during hospitalization had a statistically significant reduction in anxiety. Sand tray therapy is demonstrated to be effective in reducing the anxiety of hospitalized school age children. Sand tray therapy is highly recommended because it is effective, easy to carry out and inexpensive.

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